

Combating gender stereotypes by highlighting women's contribution to the history of societies

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1. Gender equality and gender representation in Cyprus

Despite Cyprus's legal framework on gender equality, political, socioeconomic, and cultural obstacles to women's development still exist in Cyprus. These obstacles prevent women from achieving their full potential.

Gender equality has not been a priority in Cyprus for a very long time, and there is no significant political consensus about gender equality policy. Male models dominate decision-making in all social and political structures and processes, including government and political parties, parliament, the judiciary, the economy, and the mass media, in addition to a lack of gender balance in almost all spheres of life and ineffective implementation and monitoring mechanisms.

The European Institute for Gender Equality's statistics for the 2022 index reveals that gender equality has an average percentage of 68.6% at the EU level and Cyprus reached 57.3%, which means that Cyprus is in the 7th position from the bottom. Only 25% of ministers in Cyprus are female, with 75% being men (2023). Only 14.3% of MEPs are women, compared to 85.7% of men in the parliament. The equivalent statistic for female MEPs at the European level is 33%. Women's participation in political and social life in Cyprus is only 30%. The average monthly earnings of female employees in Cyprus for the 4th quarter of 2022 are €2,024 while those of men are €2,408. Women (81%) are the ones who take care of children and the household. Additionally, it is worth mentioning that incidents of gender and domestic violence have exceeded 5,500 in the last two years.

These statistics reflect the gender inequality in Cyprus and thus, the underrepresentation of women in the public space and, also, the stereotypical structure of the private sector. In addition, statistics on the private sector of life reveal that women are primarily responsible for cooking, cleaning, and caring for the family's most vulnerable members. This demonstrates how women dominate the personal arena of life while simultaneously staying out of politics and the public sphere. These contentious facts mostly reflect the long-standing gender traditions of the countries in which female figures confront as a caregiver and as a mother in order to address the given characteristics in each gender.

2. Gender representation in history in Cyprus

Gender norms in Cyprus were well established and men and women were expected to act and behave under specific characteristics and attitudes which were considered as acceptable in the Cypriot society. Women who want to participate in politics and public life encounter a wide range of complex difficulties.

The reasons for gender inequalities and gender misrepresentation in all aspects of life are multifaceted, systemic, and structural. In an effort to understand the reality of the Cypriot society, it is crucial to point out some historical conditions of the Cypriot society's development.

Women in Cyprus face different experiences and thus, their lives are far different from men's lives and therefore, women have different needs. Especially in Cyprus in which an ethnic conflict has affected the history of the island, women have been mobilized in the dominant patriarchal and militaristic environment. Power relations were reflected also in gender relations. This interaction affected the whole structure of masculinity and femininity in the Cypriot society through ages. Historical, socio-economic, and cultural conditions affected real life experience of gender representation in Cyprus.

Prior to Cyprus's independence, women's roles were limited to the household, and only those who were better off socially and economically had access to education. Furthermore, in Cyprus, back in the time, positions of employment were divided by gender between males and females. Gender norms were also represented in the labour market, with sectors such as the "women's sectors" and the "male-dominant sectors". That means that labour sectors that were considered as female and/or male sectors of the labour market and thus, labour sectors were representing gender characteristics and attitudes.

Therefore, Cypriot women were either unpaid housewives or nurses, secretaries, teachers, or employed in agriculture and factories. And of course, women were expected to give up their career once they were getting married and/or having children and family. This is something that was happening because women were responsible to keep up with everything in the household and they were also responsible for the children's nurture. However, women were not absent from the Cypriot public sphere, historically, culturally, and socially wise. Some of the great Cypriot women's remarkable examples will be presented in the National Report of Cyprus, later in this document.

In order to change gender inequalities in both private sector, such as the family and the home, and the public sector, such as male-dominated politics and the employment sectors, feminists challenged these socially constructed dichotomies and started to promote the idea that these characteristics are a result of historical, cultural, and patriarchal structures. These goals came across with oriented strategies and struggles on legal and cultural changes.

3. Gender representation in history in Nicosia, Cyprus

The historical tapestry of Nicosia, Cyprus, boasts a nuanced narrative interwoven with the indelible marks left by women, often regrettably overshadowed by historical oversight. Institutions such as the Leventis Municipal Museum of Nicosia and the Cyprus Museum are entrusted with the responsibility of portraying the city's multifaceted history. However, these depictions frequently marginalize the pivotal role women have played. This exploration seeks to undertake a critical analysis of the portrayal of women's contributions within the historical and socio-political backdrop of Nicosia. By delving into artistic, political, and social spheres, this investigation underscores the necessity of revealing and recognizing the substantial yet frequently marginalized role of women in the annals of Nicosia's history.

Artistic Endeavors and Cultural Enrichment: The artistic landscape of Nicosia stands as a testament to the broader patterns of gender dynamics in Cyprus, revealing persistent gender inequalities. Figures such as Glyn Hughes, a British-Cypriot painter, bear witness to women's instrumental involvement in enriching the city's cultural milieu. However, their role has often been downplayed within the narratives presented by institutions like the Leventis Municipal Museum and the Cyprus Museum. An exploration of Hughes' contributions illuminates the broader significance of women's contributions to the arts in Nicosia, urging a more comprehensive representation of their endeavors in cultural narratives.

Gender and Leadership in Politics and Business: Despite advancements in women's education, Nicosia, much like Cyprus at large, remains embroiled in a gendered paradox within politics and business domains. A glass ceiling, impervious to educational attainment, prevails, thereby impeding women's ascendancy to leadership positions. Noteworthy exceptions, such as Stella Kyriakides, the former European Commissioner for Health and Food Safety, provide glimpses of progress. However, the overall representation of women in higher echelons remains

constrained. A meticulous inquiry into this conundrum uncovers systemic obstacles that hinder women's progress in domains marked by unequal gender distribution.

Gender Disparities in Political Representation: The political landscape of Nicosia epitomizes the disparities between genders, with men constituting a notable 76% of political representation, leaving women at a mere 24%. Even with the historic appointment of Mrs. Annita Dimitriou as the first female president of the parliament, and despite the fact that the capital of Cyprus, Nicosia, in the previous years had a female mayor, Mrs. Eleni Mavrou, the scales remain tipped in favor of men. A comprehensive understanding of gender dynamics necessitates an exploration beyond institutions, where women's presence reverberates through the very streets of Nicosia. Many thoroughfares, such as Xanthi Zenierou Street, Kleovoulou Street, and Eleni Vakondiou Street, serve as reminders of women's enduring influence and resilience.

Historical Vanguard: Mrs. Polyxeni Loizias: Mrs. Polyxeni Loizias, an esteemed figure in Nicosia's history, emerges as a pioneering feminist, educator, writer, and activist. Her establishment of the "Union of Greek Women," the inaugural women's gym "The Palladion," and the first women's magazine marked a radical departure from societal norms, setting the groundwork for women's emancipation across Cyprus. Loizias' transformative initiatives underscore the historical underpinnings of women's empowerment in Nicosia, transcending the limitations of traditional gender roles.

Monuments and the Gendered Narrative: The historical underrepresentation of women becomes poignantly evident when examining the commemorative landscape of Nicosia. While monuments and statues perpetuate male-centered narratives, women's invaluable contributions often remain obscured. A dearth of monuments acknowledging women's involvement in liberation struggles and other historical milestones perpetuates this gendered disparity. The review underscores the need for an inclusive commemorative landscape that faithfully reflects the diverse and vital roles women have played in shaping Nicosia's history.

4. Female footprint in Nicosia, Cyprus

4.1. Faneromeni School

The Ottoman period in Cyprus was during 1571 – 1878. During the last decades of the Ottoman period in Cyprus, primary education began to develop in the Orthodox community of the island. Faneromeni School was founded in this context, which was the first primary school for girls in Cyprus. The school was intended for the daughters of the wealthy families of the Greek Cypriot community and was founded on the initiative of Archbishop Makarios I in 1859.

The general situation for Girls Schools in Cyprus was as follows: In Limassol, the first Girls School was founded in 1911, the second in 1923, and the third in 1938. In Larnaka, the Girls School – *Parthenagogio Skalas* and Evryviadion Girls School – *Parthenagogio Evryviadion* were merged in 1906 and separated again in 1929. In Pafos, a Girls School was established in 1880. In Famagusta, a Girls School was established in 1887 and in 1926 it was divided into two schools, the second of which operated until 1941. In Kyrenia, the Girls School was opened in 1887 (Michailidou 2017).¹

Regarding Faneromenis School, during its first year 35 female students were studying in all six classes of the school. Twenty years later, in 1880, the School had 152 female students and it was the only school for female students in Nicosia. During its first years the classes were reading, writing, mathematics, religion classes, Greek history classes and handcraft classes. Female students learned the values that a girl should follow in order to compromise with society's values. Such values were modesty, care, diligence and obedience.

Back at that time, women were considered ashamed to work. Because of that, the school committee used to give scholarships to girls with fewer opportunities and from poor villages. In this way, they gave them the opportunity to be educated in order to become teachers.

Inside Faneromeni's School the first higher institution for female teachers was established back in 1903. Female teachers used to be paid less than male teachers and also, married female teachers weren't allowed to work and they were obligated to stop working as teachers when they were planning to get married.

The Higher institution was shut down in 1937 and the building was a part of the Pancyprian Highschool institute which welcomed only female students. In 1975, was the only year that

¹ Girls Education in Cyprus. Maria Michaelidou (2017).

the school was a mixed-gender school. Back then, directress and female teachers of Faneromeni's School, had a crucial involvement in the development of women's associations. One example was Theano Parouti – Liasidou, who was a directress of the School from 1887 until 1901. Later she quitted because she was about to get married, and Eleni Christou was placed as a directress of the school. Some years later, in 1914, they managed to create a women's association in Nicosia.

In recent years Faneromeni's school had a kindergarten, primary school, and high school. Now, it works as a department of the School of Architecture of the University of Cyprus.

4.2. Anna Tiggidou, the first female scientist in Cyprus

Anna Tiggidou² was studying in Faneromeni's School. It is said that Anna Tiggidou is the first Cypriot female scientist. Anna was born in Lefkara (Larnaka) and she studied Dentistry at the "Ecole Dentaire de Paris" (School of Dentistry of Paris). When she completed her studies in France, she ended up in Larnaka where she had her own dental office.

4.3. Ourania Kokkinou Statue

Next to the entrance of the school is one of the few statues in Nicosia dedicated to a woman. It represents Ourania Kokkinou, the first female theologian in Cyprus³. She was also a directress of the Pancyprian Female Gymnasium in the Kykkos area. She was a member of EOKA and was imprisoned for her activities.

4.4. The Royal Hall

The Royal Hall used to be one of the first cinemas in Nicosia until the end of the 40s. Today, the same building is being used as an event venue.

On the 25th of April 1955, the Pancyprian Protest of Female Workers took place there and the protest was about social security and for a better working environment. In the announcement, they were mentioning the right to be absent from work when sick, the security of the widows and orphans, and equal payment between men and women.

On the 9th of July 1959, there was another crucial event in this place. The founding conference of the Pancyprian Federation of Women's associations took place there. At this conference there were 1500 female participants from around Cyprus. This conference was about the right of vote for women, for equal rights between men and women in social and political life, for

² Find online: <https://larnakaonline.com.cy/2016/02/22/25297/>

³ Find online: <https://www.bigcyprus.com.cy/el/destinations/nicosia/mnimeio-oyranias-kokkinoy-sti-leykosia>

social security, for legislative security of mothers and children, for equal payment between men and women, for whole education and professional skills of children, for the security of all female workers, and for a peaceful and independent Cyprus.

4.5. Xanthis Xenierou Avenue

The Royal Hall is located in Xanthis Xenierou Avenue. Xanthis Xenierou Avenue is one of the few avenues which is named after a female figure. Xanthi Xenierou is the refined creation of Elisabeth Santi-Lomaca, who was a thinker of Cypriot descent. She was married to the French Ludovico Senié and she moved to Paris and died there in 1808. She is a famous highbrow woman known for “Literary Saloons” and the mother of the French poet André Chénier.

The “Literary Saloons” were the houses of educated women who invited different highbrow people in meetings for sharing ideas and communication. These women, named as “salonnières”, helped in the diffusion of the Enlightenment Ideas when these Ideas were still prosecuted by the French authorities.

The well-known figures of the Enlightenment such as Voltaire and Rousseau, were believers of the idea that women belonged to the private sector and were unable to participate in the public sphere and in politics. Thus, even though women were part of diffusing the Enlightenment ideas and in the French revolution, it is known that the revolution denied their participation in politics by voting and later on, in 1793, the revolutionary government preached every female political action.

4.6. The Shelter for working women

The Shelter for working women, has been located in Sokratous 19th Avenue since 1960. Anastasia Koumbaridou had the idea for this initiative, since the women that worked in the area were coming from rural areas and they didn’t have any place to rest during their break from work.

Anastasia Koumbaridou, asked from the Faneromenis Church to give this place to women for this purpose. Back then, there were beds and other facilities and up to 75 women were having a place to relax and eat during their work-break times. Also, it was also a place where female workers and their trade unions had the opportunity to meet and talk about any working issues. Today, the Shelter is still working but not in the same dynamic as the earlier years.

4.7. Women’s Bazaar – ‘ginekopazaro’

Back in the time, women were gathering at the end of Ledras Street to sell their own products. There you could find women from all over Cyprus, from the villages and the rural areas. This

was a way of survival back then. Women were getting there using their donkeys and they were sitting on the floor with the staff they made. Some of the selling goods were hand-woven textile, silk textiles and cotton. All these were handcrafts by the women. We don't really know the exact time that the '*Ginekopazaro*' started, however, there are some clues that this was happening even from the Franks period (13th – 15th century). Then, during the early years of the 20th century, the women's bazaar was a crucial part of Nicosia's bazaars.

In 1922, the Faneromeni's Church Committee decided to build a specific place to host the women's bazaar. This was an initiative in order to protect the women from the sunny and/or the rainy days. The new women's bazaar was launched in 1924 at the end of Ledras Street. '*Ginekopazaro*' stopped working in June, 1958 because of the British Colony and the restrictions of that period. In 1969 this building was demolished. However, in 2008, the '*ginekopazaro*' was renewed in a more modern way, back at the place when the first women's bazaar was taking place (at the place where the Büyük Hamam is nowadays). This was an initiative of Amvrosia's Sakkadas, who had also a shop in Ledras Street and she came up with this idea to motivate people to reach this area more.

4.8. Ledras Street – Loukia Nikolaidou, the first female artist in Cyprus

Ledras Street is a major shopping street in central Nicosia. Around Ledras Street, Loukia Nikolaidou, the first female painter in Cyprus, had one of her first exhibitions in 1934. Loukia Nikolaidou⁴, was the first female painter that studied Art abroad. She was born in 1909 in Limassol and died in 1994, at Penn in England. Back in the time, she decided to go abroad, in Paris and study Art.

During that time, that was a very brave decision since decisions like that were not aligned with what the society would expect from Loukia to do. Societal stereotypes and gender norms would expect Loukia to stay at home and start her own family.

She studied in Paris at the Colarossi Academy and then she continued to the School Nationale Superieure des Beaux-Arts. She came back to Cyprus in 1933 and she made her first three exhibitions, both in Nicosia and Limassol. The exhibition in Nicosia, was around Ledras Street, the exact location is unknown. The exhibitions were in 1934, 1935 and 1936. Later on, she continued with other great and famous exhibitions both personal and in collaboration with other famous artists.

⁴ Find online: <https://www.philenews.com/politismos/article/548024/i-protoporos-loukia-nikola%CE%90dou/>

In 1992, there was an exhibition dedicated to her work at the National Gallery in Nicosia.

4.9. 'Aischilou' Avenue

This avenue is an opportunity to learn about women and theatre in Nicosia. From the one side of this Avenue is the back aspect of the Faneromenis' School and on the other is the place where the Papadopoulo's Theatre used to be.

Back in the time, in the 40s, women actors were a big taboo for that period. Male actors were playing even the female roles. In 1891, there was the first time that a Cypriot woman actor was playing in the theatre scene. This girl was Polixeni Fisentzidi, a student of the Faneromeni's Female School. The next years were more theatrical acts from both female and male students.

The Papadopoulo's Theatre was in this Avenue from 1899 until 1967. It was the most valuable theatre of Nicosia and there were a lot of theatrical acts in which female actors were participating, both from abroad and Cyprus. Unfortunately, in 1967 the owners decided to demolish it in order to build shops.

**Faneromeni's School, Ourania Kokkinou Statue, The Royal Hall, Xanthis Xenierou Avenue, The Shelter for working women, Women's Bazaar, 'Aischilou' Avenue, are places discovered after the research of the Centre for Gender Equality and History, in 2016, in the concept of a tour with the name "Reviving the invisible history of women: A walk in another Nicosia" (Oct. 2016)*

4.10. Zena Palace – Theognosia Zena Kanther

Zena Palaca is one of the first cinemas that existed in Cyprus, located in the center of Nicosia. It took its name from its owner, Princess Zena Kanther De Tyras⁵, who was born in Tala, Paphos, on July 3, 1927, in a poor family. In 1967, Zena Kanther, after being spiritually adopted by Prince Paul Palaiologos-Krive, acquired a noble title, and became "Princess de Tyras." Since then, along with the enormous wealth she gained from her marriage to the American millionaire Christian Kanther, Zena Kanther has been actively involved in significant philanthropic activities. She is the most prominent Cypriot philanthropist and benefactor of Cyprus, who also volunteered in the liberation struggle against the British

4.11. Lady of Lapithos Euphrosyne Proestou

During the Turkish invasion on August 6, 1974, 12 soldiers were cut off and trapped behind enemy lines. These soldiers were discovered by a 74-year-old woman named Euphrosyne Proestou at that time. She hid them in a small cave near her home and took care of them for an entire month, all while evading the watchful eyes of the numerous Turkish forces already

⁵ Find online: <https://www.cyprusalive.com/el/princess-zena-kanther-de-tyras>

present in Lapithos. The Turks became suspicious of her actions and started interrogating her. She endured horrific torture. They stripped her, tied her behind a military jeep, and dragged her on the asphalt until her skin turned crimson from the wounds and blood. Despite the severe mistreatment, she didn't utter a word. When she passed away in 1993 at the age of 90, her 12 "adopted" soldiers, as she considered them her children, erected a monument in her honor in front of the Ledra Palace, overlooking the enslaved Pentadaktylos mountain range⁶.

4.12. Liberty Monument

The Liberty Monument was erected in 1973 to honor the fighters of EOKA during the Cyprus Liberation Struggle of 1955-1959. It is located within the Venetian walls. The grand monument contains several statues. At the top of the structure, a statue represents the "Clocks of Freedom" above two heroic EOKA fighters opening the chains to unlock the prison gate, allowing Greek Cypriot captives, farmers, and clergy to escape from British rule. The bronze figures of men and women of different ages are vividly depicted emerging from the darkness of the prison after a long time and witnessing the light of day. The fact that the official inauguration for this monument never took place due to the tragic events of 1974 is a poignant irony. Just when the Cypriot Hellenism saw the light of the sun after a long time and was heading towards the ultimate good of freedom, the violent Turkish invasion suddenly overturned their hopes. The monument becomes a timeless symbol of struggle and hope for freedom.

4.13. Elpinikis Street

The street "Elpinikis" in Nicosia took its name from Elpiniki, who was an ancient Greek woman from Sicily and the Cypriot city of Salamis. She is known for her contribution during the Trojan War, as she provided significant financial support to the Greek warriors who fought against Troy. The choice of the street's name may have been made to honor the mythical or historical figure of Elpiniki and to highlight the cultural richness of ancient Greece and Cyprus.

4.14. Arsinoyis Street

The Arsinoyis Street took its name from Arsinoyi, a historical figure from ancient Cyprus. Arsinoyi was the wife of King Leontokrates of Cyprus during the Ptolemaic dynasty. Also known as Arsinoyi II, she was the queen of Cyprus in the 3rd century BCE and had significant

⁶ Find online: <https://www.philenews.com/kipros/koinonia/article/1373529/martiria-gia-tous-12-ethnofrouous-pou-diesose-i-kira-tis-lapithou/>

influence in the political and cultural affairs of that era. During her reign, she conducted numerous excavations and projects to improve Cypriot society. The street that bears her name recognizes the importance of Arsinoyi in the history of Cyprus and the Ptolemaic period, while also honoring her contributions to ancient Cypriot culture.

4.15. Σωματείο Ελληνίδων Κυριών Μάνα

The Association was founded in March 1933 by a group of women with the purpose of philanthropy and care for mothers and children. As part of its contribution, the Association has been diligently supporting working mothers through the establishment of nurseries and canteens and continues to do so until today.

4.16. Pancyprian Federation of Women's Organizations

The "Pancyprian Federation of Women's Organizations" is an organization founded in Cyprus at the year of 1959 with the aim of promoting women's rights and empowering women's voices and participation in society. The Pancyprian Federation of Women's Organizations operates throughout Cyprus and collaborates with various women's organizations and communities on the island. The Pancyprian Federation of Women's Organizations organizes events, conferences, seminars, and educational programs to raise awareness among the public about issues concerning women and to promote gender equality. Additionally, it cooperates with other entities and organizations to achieve its goals in advocating for women's rights in Cyprus.

4.17. Eleftheria Square

Eleftheria Square is a central square located in Nicosia. It is one of the most well-known and vibrant areas of the city, serving as a hub for social, cultural, and commercial activities. Freedom Square boasts impressive architecture with various buildings and monuments surrounding it. It is a beloved destination for both locals and tourists, where they can enjoy the hospitality of the Cypriot capital, go shopping, savor local cuisine, and experience the liveliness of the old city around them. Additionally, the square often hosts various events, exhibitions, musical performances, and festivals, offering a unique experience to its visitors.

4.18. Kostas and Rita Severis Foundation

The "Kostas and Rita Severis Foundation" is a philanthropic organization founded in Cyprus with the aim of promoting arts, culture, and education. The foundation was established by Kostas and Rita Severis, two prominent Cypriot philanthropists, who dedicated their lives to

the promotion of the country's artistic and cultural heritage. The foundation operates as a cultural center and advocates various initiatives to support and develop Cyprus' artistic community. It offers scholarships and financial support to young artists, promotes exhibitions, theatrical events, musical performances, and facilitates cultural programs and events for the public. Additionally, the Kostas and Rita Severis Foundation manages and preserves cultural landmarks and historic buildings in Cyprus, thus promoting the heritage and cultural legacy of the region. The foundation constitutes a significant contribution to Cyprus' cultural and artistic life and fosters artistic creation and culture in the area.

4.19. Catherine Cornaro

Catherine Cornaro was the Queen of Cyprus and the wife of Peter I of Cyprus. Their marriage took place in 1382, and she became the Queen of Cyprus. Peter I and Catherine ruled the kingdom with dignity and success, strengthening Cyprus' relations with neighboring countries and promoting the prosperity of its people. After Peter I's death in 1392, Catherine continued to govern Cyprus as the Queen Mother for their son, James II. However, in 1398, James II removed Catherine from power and exiled her to Sicily, where she passed away at around the age of 60. Catherine Cornaro was known for her kindness and love for the people of Cyprus. Her reign marked a period of prosperity and cultural development for the Cypriot people.

4.20. Diamantou Charalambous

Women's footprint in all the efforts of changing the working conditions in Cyprus, was decisive. Back in the days, women were active in trade unions and fought under extremely difficult conditions towards a more human working environment and for better income and for working rights.

In the strike struggles of the silk factory of Geroskipou in 1927, the spinning mill P. Ioannou in Famagusta in 1938, in the bunches of the Limassol and Larnaca factories in 1942 and 1945 respectively, in the mines of Mavrovounio-Xeros and Asbestos in 1948, in the sectors of clothing, footwear, construction and agriculture and in so many others in the 1950s and 1960s, women gave their "presence" en masse, militantly, worthily and exemplarily.

During this period Cyprus was under British Colonial. Back on these years, Cyprus was a place of constant strikes and demands for change. Diamantou Charalambous was a construction worker in May 1940. This was something really revolutionary for the social norms of those years. Diamantou combatted all gender stereotypes and refused to respond to any of the

gender norms that wanted women to stay in the private sphere, as good mothers and good housewives.

In May 1940 Diamantou Charalambous took part in a demonstration of unemployed construction workers in Nicosia. She was savagely beaten by the police for taking part in this demonstration, in which the workers demanded that the colonial government open jobs for the unemployed. Unfortunately, there aren't any data for the exact place that this took place. However, the first trade unions were located at Metaksa Square, as the Eleftheria Square used to be called.

4.21. Marika Kotopouli Street

Marika Kotopouli, one of the most important figures of modern Greek theatre, was born in Athens on 3 May 1887 to theatrical parents, Dimitrios and Eleni Kotopouli. Although a Greek figure, her descent to Cyprus in 1927 is one of the most important moments in the history of Cypriot theatre, which was warmly welcomed by journalists, poets, people of the arts and letters. In the centre of Nicosia, there is Marika Kotopouli Street.

Marika Kotopouli began her theatrical career in 1897 with her parents' company, performing outside Athens. In 1902 she joined Christomanos' "New Stage", but quickly moved to the "Royal Theatre of Athens". In 1906 she travelled to Paris with her cousin, actor Petros Nikolaou.

Her career began in 1908, when she formed a company with the comedian Konstantinos Sayor. In 1911, she founded a new company with the comedian Ioannis Papaioannou, presenting Hofmannsthal's Elektra at the Attikon. In 1912, she formed her first personal company and acquired her own theatrical home, the "Marika Kotopouli Theatre", in Omonia Square.

In 1921, she was awarded the Golden Cross of George I and in 1923, she received the Award of Arts and Letters from the Ministry of Education. In 1937, after the abandonment of the "Theatre Kotopouli", he founded the "Rex" on Panepistimiou Street, presenting the play "Elizabeth" by André José. In 1939, the thirty-year anniversary of her thirtieth anniversary was celebrated and her company became a semi-public company.

During the Occupation, she retired from theatrical performances and helped several of her leftist colleagues. She belonged to the right and supported royalty. After liberation, she was appointed chairman of the artistic committee and a member of the board of directors of the

National Theatre, which was renamed the Royal Theatre after the restoration of royalty in 1946.

Marika Kotopouli died suddenly of cardiac arrest in Athens on 11 September 1954, at the age of 67.

4.22. Axiotheas' Street

Axiothea was an ancient heroine of Cyprus, wife of Nicocles, the last descendant of the dynasty of the Kiniraidis. In the 4th century BC, when the Egyptian king Ptolemy I invaded with his army and captured Nicocles' palace, causing his death, his wife, Αξιοthea, chose to commit suicide rather than suffer the humiliation of captivity.

Thus, when Sesshea learned of Nicocles' death, she called upon all the women of the palace not to tolerate the disgrace and fall into the hands of their enemies. And as none of their opponents conquered, the women closed and barricaded the women's room and went up to the roof of the palace. There, before the eyes of the assembled multitude, Merithea slaughtered her unmarried daughters, and the wives of Nicocles' brothers followed her example, slaughtering their own children. Then they set fire to the thatched roof and some committed suicide by falling into the flames and others with swords. The last to commit suicide was Αξιοthea, giving a sword to herself and jumping into the fire, lest the opponents keep a dead body. Nicocles' brothers, after all these evils, set fire to the palace and were themselves slain.

5. Nicosia's practices in disseminating gender balanced history

Women's presence in history is a controversial debate through ages. On the one hand there is the opinion that suggests that women were not active back in the ages of city's histories due to the gender stereotypes and gender norms that women were considering as part of the private sphere and thus we don't read, study, or hear their achievements in the public sphere. However, is this really the case? It is a common truth that women, half of the population, are persistently excluded and under-represented.

Hence, it is a logical assumption that countries and cities around the world would face a lack of good examples of city's or country's practices of women's achievement diffusion. Gender visibility is a crucial strategy to promote gender equality in European democracies.

The ability of Cyprus's civil society to successfully mobilize and advocate for changes in policy on gender equality problems is still limited and disorganized. However, most recently, human rights NGOs and women's movements in Cyprus have started to change this narrative and they have managed to enhance gender equality and women's visibility as a part of the public debate and the public sphere. These initiatives succeeded in increasing the interest of the society in gender inclusion and in human rights.

However, more actions are needed to establish gender visibility and gender perspective in a more efficient way. Women's visibility in countries and cities' history will be more established when more initiatives take place, however, the diffusion of such initiatives is also crucial for the dissemination of the knowledge and in order to inspire for more actions of the states and the civil society.

An important initiative in disseminating gender balanced history in Nicosia was part of one-years' activities of the Center for Gender Equality and History (K.I.I.F.) back in 2016. This initiative was developing free tours around the city in response to specific points of interest regarding aspects of women's history. The Center for Gender Equality and History was the first organisation that organized such walks in Cyprus.

The content of the tours was created after extended research and the walks were organized and presented by a group of women, all members and/or volunteers of K.I.I.F. The walks were around the old city of Nicosia, and specifically, monuments, statues, street names etc., with gender perspective were presented to the participants. Gender history was the general subject of these walking tours.

This initiative gave the opportunity to the public to get more information about the city's history without exclusions or misrepresentations of any social groups of the society. By using new and inspiring tools of knowledge dissemination the Center for Gender Equality and History managed to get the public's interest and of course, the researchers of the organisation, managed to collect useful and unknown information about women's presence in the capital of Cyprus, Nicosia.

6. Local strategies

The local community in Nicosia, Cyprus, takes various approaches to preserve and share its history, including maintaining heritage sites, conducting historical tours, and organizing cultural events. However, a closer examination reveals a lack of representation of women in these historical narratives. It is worth exploring the stories of women associated with these places. For instance, Maria Iacovou, a professor of archaeology at the University of Cyprus, has significantly enhanced our understanding of ancient Cyprus, showcasing the potential of such explorations.

Nicosia hosts significant cultural institutions, such as the Leventis Municipal Museum of Nicosia and the Cyprus Museum. These establishments play a crucial role in safeguarding and disseminating the city's history. However, there is a need to assess how they portray the contributions of women in this historical narrative.

Nicosia boasts a diverse collection of historical and cultural sites that weave together the city's rich past. Notable landmarks like the Venetian Walls, Famagusta Gate, and the Archbishop's Palace serve as tangible reminders of Nicosia's history. Nonetheless, these landmarks often feature stories that disproportionately center around male figures, leaving women's contributions in the background.

Consider Maria Iacovou, an archaeology professor at the University of Cyprus. Her work has significantly expanded our knowledge of ancient Cyprus. However, how well-known are her achievements among Nicosia residents and visitors? How frequently are her contributions showcased in tours or exhibitions? While these landmarks offer insights into the city's history, they can unintentionally perpetuate a limited, gender-biased perspective if they fail to include women's stories.

Addressing this imbalance necessitates reevaluating the methods employed to promote Nicosia's history. This might involve designing guided tours that emphasize women's contributions or organizing exhibitions dedicated specifically to women's roles in Nicosia's history. These strategies could contribute to a more balanced representation of the city's historical narrative.

When implementing these measures, it is crucial for them to garner appropriate visibility. In particular, it is essential for local residents to learn about Cyprus's history. Additionally, when new historical findings emerge, disseminating them through mass media channels can ensure

widespread awareness and recognition, ultimately acknowledging the efforts of diligent individuals. The presence of women in these significant positions should serve as an inspiring example to be emulated across various fields.

7. Focus Groups with Young People: Analyses and results

7.1. Findings on 'Relevance with the field of History'

The participants of the focus group, despite not having deep relevance or specialization in the field of history, displayed a strong interest in the topic. Their connection to history was mainly shaped by their experiences attending history classes during their time in high school. This foundation in history education served as a starting point for their engagement in discussions related to historical narratives and women's contributions.

7.2. Findings on 'Level of knowledge in history'

Within the focus group, the young participants highlighted a significant disparity between the representation of women and men in history textbooks. They emphasized that history textbooks primarily focused on male figures, leaving women significantly underrepresented both in terms of textual content and visual depictions. This exclusion perpetuated a historical narrative that marginalized and overlooked the substantial contributions of women. The participants expressed their inability to recall notable women figures from their history textbooks without resorting to external sources. Recognizing the pivotal role textbooks play in shaping their understanding, the participants underscored the urgent need for increased visibility of women's achievements in history education. They suggested that a comprehensive integration of women's stories and accomplishments into textbooks would be crucial to challenge gender stereotypes and ensure a more balanced representation of historical narratives.

7.3. Findings on 'Methods to promote women's footprint in history'

The participants exhibited enthusiasm for the proposal to create an interactive online map designed to promote awareness of women's contributions in history. They acknowledged the potency of visual representation and endorsed the inclusion of information about significant women from diverse time periods and geographical regions. This interactive map was seen as an effective tool to engage users and facilitate their exploration and learning about women's historical impact.

During discussions, the participants introduced the concept of a historical classification system or timeline. This system was suggested as a means to categorize women's contributions within specific historical contexts, aiding users in comprehending the significance of their achievements across various time periods. By showcasing women's diverse accomplishments throughout history, this approach aimed to foster a deeper appreciation for the evolution of women's roles.

Recognizing the influential role of visual media, the participants advocated for the promotion and screening of films and documentaries highlighting the stories of inspirational women. Additionally, they proposed the organization of art exhibitions showcasing the works of both historical and contemporary female artists. These strategies were deemed effective in

captivating the attention of young people while delivering impactful narratives about women's historical and cultural contributions.

Lastly, the idea of a treasure hunt as an educational activity was discussed within the focus group. This innovative approach was considered an engaging method for participants to explore cities while learning about women's history. By utilizing interactive technology, such as mobile applications, participants could navigate through specific locations, completing challenges and answering questions related to women's historical achievements. The potential inclusion of a knowledgeable guide to oversee the treasure hunt was suggested to enhance the experience by providing additional insights and guidance.

In conclusion, the focus group findings highlight the need for an overhaul in history education to rectify the gender imbalance and ensure the recognition of women's contributions throughout history. The participants' recommendations emphasize the importance of diverse educational tools, visual media, interactive technologies, and engaging activities to promote a more accurate and inclusive understanding of women's historical impact.

8. Focus Groups with Stakeholders: Analyses and results

8.1. Findings on 'Relevance with the field of History'

All the stakeholders that were participated in the Focus Group were representing Institutions, Research Centres and Civil Society's organisations in the field of History, Gender, Human Rights, and some of them were also part of Local Authorities.

Three of them were members of Research Centres and Organisations that implements research in Gender History and in Human Rights. Four of them were members of Human Rights Organisations and groups of Civil Society. One of them is currently working in a

university and specifically in the Department of Diversity and one of the participants were the first ever female Mayor of Nicosia, Cyprus' capital.

All the institutions that were represented in the Focus Group are working to promote gender perspective each in their own field of interest. Their actions are addressing gender equality by raising equal gender visibility through multisector initiatives. Some of the fields that they are working on are gender & sports, gender & culture, gender & working rights, gender & history and gender & media. In each area of interest, the participants are working hard by developing activities, projects and local actions through the lens of gender perspective and by promoting female visibility in order to combat gender misrepresentation.

8.2. Findings on 'History through the lens of their expertise'

Participants agreed that history is a gender biased topic which is written by the already male-dominant civil groups of societies. All participants also, agreed on the difficulties that they are facing when they are trying to implement the gender perspective aspect in their research field. Furthermore, they added that finding information related to the female's footprint in history is really challenging.

Thus, some of their findings are gender biased. Some of the participants, added that these challenges become from the lack of state mechanisms on recording women's contribution in history and they pointed out the lack of funding on such initiatives as a crucial milestone on these procedures.

The participants also mentioned, that, gender stereotypes are strictly rooted in the Cypriot society and thus, there is this narrative that women were only placed in the private sector and that's the reason why institutions and researchers finding it hard to find information and data. However, they acknowledged the fact this is not something that is only a myth because based on their findings and their expertise in the field they often find evidence of women's examples who managed to gain their own space in their field of interest without anyone giving them any opportunities. Additionally, gender norms of what is considered as a "great achievement" reflects on what is being archived and what is not.

The participants agreed that even though they are expertise in this specific field of research, they believe that there is still a lot of lack of knowledge regarding women who contributed either collectively or anonymously.

8.3. Findings on ‘Experience with young people in the field of History’

Participants of the Focus Group mentioned the crucial role of the education system when it comes to knowledge, information and opportunities. Young people seem to be interested to learn more about gender and female’s footprint in history, however they don’t have the right tools to gain such knowledge neither they are given the space they need nor the encouragement or the support.

Some of the participants mentioned some challenges that they have noticed throughout their experience when working with young people. They pointed out that, nowadays, young people are born, raised and influenced by the male-dominant narrative and that is really challenging when it comes to topics such as gender equality. Young people believe that all people have equal rights and equal opportunities and thus, they don’t feel the need to act towards gender equality.

However, stakeholders mentioned that their experience with this group of people, shows that young people who have developed social voluntary action, are more sensible to such issues. While all stakeholders agreed that they detect interest in young people’s opinions in gender perspective topics, however, despite that, they still find difficulties on how to influence and affect them more.

8.4. Findings on ‘Women’s footprint in history’

Stakeholders that have participated in the Focus Group have mentioned the following women’s footprint examples in history:

- i. The building where the first women telephone operators were working (CYTA Building, Nicosia, Cyprus)
- ii. Electra Building (close to the Ledra Palas)
- iii. Female school ‘*Parthenagogio*’
- iv. The Royal Hall (venue of the first women’s organisation conference)
- v. Vasilissis Olgas Street (‘*Vasilissis*’ comes from the Greek word ‘*vasilissa*’ which means “Queen”)
- vi. Vasilissis Friderikis Street
- vii. Melina Merkouri Street
- viii. Evgenia Theodotou Street

8.5. Suggestions on tools to promote women's footprint in history

8.5.1. General Suggestions

- i. Non-formal education tools.
- ii. Participatory education to increase interest.
- iii. Experiential learning.

8.5.2. Digital Tools

- i. Audio-visual material
- ii. Statues & monuments with scan signs where the visitor could scan and listen the background story.
- iii. Story telling & use the Cypriot dialect in order to attract the young people more.
- iv. The developed map could be combined with videos.

8.5.3. Collaborations

- i. Nicosia Municipality
- ii. All of the organisations & institutions that were participating in the Focus Group stated their desire to contribute in any way to the projects' activities.

9. Conclusions

In Cyprus women and girls faces different kind barriers towards gender equality. Political, socioeconomic, and cultural elements affect the level of gender equality in the island. Gender norms are well rooted in the Cypriot societies and women and men are often obligated to respond to specific gender characteristics in order to fit to society's expectations.

Furthermore, women's visibility is limited. Women's portrayal is crucial especially in areas that women are mis-represented and that can have a negative effect in the empowerment of young people. Stakeholders in Cyprus acknowledged the fact that young people are interested

in get more knowledge about women's footprint in Cypriot history. However, they are not provided with access in this knowledge.

In addition, Cypriot stakeholders states that they face different kind of challenges. The main challenge is that funding for specified research in gender-based history is limited as well as limited funding for more initiatives and more national projects.

Findings through the desk research and through the Focus Groups' analysis shows that there is a gap in the gender-based knowledge in history. This confirms that HerStory project's objectives are important and necessary to improve gender equality and to address the empowerment of young people and to inspire stakeholder's actions. The outcomes of the HerStory project will reinforce gender equality and will provide access to knowledge about women's footprint in European cities' history.